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Assistant Professor,
Department of Geography
Government Vidarbha
Institute of Science and
Humanities
(Autonomous), Amravati
Email:
pravinmatode777@gmail.com

Address for correspondence:
Dr. Pravin M. Matode
Assistant Professor, Department of
Geography, Government Vidarbha
Institute of Science and Humanities
(Autonomous), Amravati
Email: pravinmatode777@gmail.com

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Spatial Patterns of Gender Disparity in Literacy - A Geographical Study of Amravati District

Dr. Pravin M. Matode

Abstract

The social and economic dynamism of a country is linked to literacy and educational development. Social transitions over time, the march toward modernization, and the flow of new ideas are interrelated with literacy and education. Education forms the foundation of development, but gender inequality often deprives women of educational opportunities. In the urban areas of Amravati district, the availability of educational facilities has resulted in the highest female literacy rate, while rural areas face challenges such as a lack of educational resources, conservative mindsets, poverty, and superstitions, leading to lower literacy rates.

In 2011, Amravati tehsil recorded the highest literacy rate (81.88%) in the district, whereas Dharni (64.49%) and Chikhaladara (65.17%) tehsils had the lowest. The literacy disparity index was the lowest in Amravati tehsil (0.053) and highest in Dharni (0.140) and Chikhaladara (0.147), indicating lesser gender disparity in literacy in Amravati tehsil compared to the other two. Across the 11 tehsils, a medium level of disparity index distribution was observed.

Dharni and Chikhaladara, characterized by tribal-dominated areas, superstitions, remote mountainous regions, and lack of transportation and communication facilities, have the highest gender disparity in literacy rates. In contrast, Amravati tehsil shows the least gender disparity in literacy. Amravati city, within this tehsil, has extensive educational infrastructure ranging from pre-primary to higher education across various disciplines. As a major educational hub in western Vidarbha, it has fostered progressive attitudes towards women's education, thereby reducing the gender disparity in literacy rates.

Key Words: Literacy Rate, Gender Disparity Index, Gender Gap, Patterns, Comparative Analysis, Educational Development

Introduction:

Literacy is a fundamental right of every human being and plays a crucial role in their holistic development. It is considered a key indicator of a country's social and economic progress. In India, significant gender disparities are observed in rural and urban literacy rates. Factors such as a lack of educational resources, conservative societal beliefs, lack of awareness about education, and poverty contribute to gender inequality in literacy rates. There is a wide gap between male and female literacy rates in the country, with male literacy being considerably higher than female literacy.

Literacy significantly impacts key demographic factors like fertility, mortality, migration, marriage, and living standards, influencing the dynamics of population growth. In Amravati district, gender disparities in literacy rates are evident, with urban areas showing lesser disparity compared to rural regions. In 2011, the male literacy rate in the district was recorded at 91.46%, while the female literacy rate was 83.10%. In Maharashtra, the gender disparity in literacy was 12.51%, while at the national level, it stood at 16.5%.

The literacy and educational levels of a population reflect the developmental trajectory of a nation. In this context, it becomes essential to study the gender-based literacy rates and their disparities in Amravati district, which is the focus of this brief research essay.

Study Area:

Amravati district, located in the northern part of Maharashtra, covers 3.98% of the state's total geographical area. The district is divided into 14 tehsils and 6 sub-divisions. It is recognized as a progressive district in the Vidarbha region, both in terms of trade and education. Geographically, Amravati district lies between 20°32' to 21°46' North latitude and 76°37' to 78°27' East longitude, with a total area of 12,235 sq. km.

The district is bordered by Madhya Pradesh and the Satpuda mountain ranges to the north, and by Akola, Washim, and Yavatmal districts to the south. Among the tehsils, Dharni and Chikhaladara stand out for their significant Scheduled Tribe population compared to other tehsils.

Research Aims and Objectives:

The primary objectives of this short research paper are as follows:

1. To understand the disparity in male and female literacy rates in Amravati district as per the 2011 census.
2. To evaluate gender-based disparities in literacy in Amravati district and analyze the inequalities.
3. To study the spatial patterns of gender disparities in literacy within Amravati district.

Database & Methodology:

The secondary statistical data and information required for this brief research essay were collected from the Amravati District Census Handbook-2011, Maharashtra Economic Survey, socio-economic reviews, published reports, and printed literature. To study the tehsil-wise literacy rates and gender disparities in literacy in Amravati district, the following formulas were utilized:

1. Literacy Rate:

$$\text{Literacy Rate} = \left(\frac{\text{Literate Population}}{\text{Total Population}} \right) \times 100$$

2. Disparity Index:

$$\text{Disparity Index} = \log \frac{x_2}{x_1} + \log \left(\frac{200-x_1}{200-x_2} \right)$$

These formulas were employed to evaluate and analyze gender-based disparities in literacy rates of Amravati district.

Tehsil-wise Literacy in Amravati District – (Year 2011)

Table number 1 presents the tehsil-wise and gender-wise literacy rates in the Amravati district. From this, it is evident that there is inequality in literacy rates between males and females across the 14 tehsils of Amravati district.

Table 1: Tehsil-wise Literacy Details of Amravati District (Year 2011)

Sr. No.	Tehsil	Total Literacy	Male Literacy	Female Literacy	Male Literacy %	Female Literacy %	Gender Gap	Gender Disparity Index	Literacy Rate %
1	Dharni	119,097	67,589	51,508	36.60	27.89	8.71	0.140	64.48
2	Chikhaldara	77,436	44,187	33,249	37.19	27.98	9.21	0.147	65.17
3	AnjangaonSurji	127,438	68,093	59,345	42.31	36.88	5.43	0.075	79.20
4	Achalpur	221,993	118,975	103,018	42.57	36.86	5.71	0.077	79.43
5	Chandur Bazaar	154,699	82,750	71,949	42.16	36.66	5.50	0.075	78.82
6	Morshi	143,638	77,094	66,544	42.24	36.46	5.18	0.078	78.71
7	Warud	173,378	93,247	80,131	41.44	35.61	5.83	0.081	77.07
8	Tivsa	82,042	44,149	37,893	42.16	36.18	5.98	0.082	78.34
9	Amravati	645,464	338,423	307,041	42.92	38.94	3.98	0.053	81.88
10	Bhankuli	89,467	48,330	41,137	42.72	36.36	6.36	0.087	79.10
11	Daryapur	138,689	74,181	64,508	42.37	36.85	5.53	0.076	79.22
12	Nandgaon Kha.	99,742	53,964	45,778	41.57	35.26	6.31	0.087	76.84
13	Chandur Railway	75,307	40,551	34,756	41.84	35.86	5.98	0.081	77.71
14	Dhamangaon Railway	103,485	55,671	47,814	41.88	35.97	5.91	0.082	77.86
Total		2251875	1,207,104	1,044,771	91.46	83.10	5.62	0.077	77.96

Source: Amravati District Census Handbook - 2011.

In Amravati district, the highest literacy rate is observed in Amravati tehsil at 81.88%, while the lowest literacy rates are found in the tribal-dominated regions of Dharni (64.49%) and Chikhaldara (65.17%). Amravati tehsil also has the highest literate population (645,464) compared to other tehsils, while Chikhaldara has the lowest (77,436).

Chikhaldara and Dharni tehsils fall under the category with a literacy rate below 70%. In contrast, 11 tehsils fall under the medium literacy rate category (70-80%), including Nandgaon Khandeshwar (76.84%), Chandur Railway (77.71%), Dhamangaon Railway (77.86%), Chandur Bazar (78.82%), Morshi (78.71%), Tivsa (78.35%), Daryapur (79.22%), Bhatkuli (79.10%), Warud (79.06%), Anjangaon (79.20%), and Achalpur (79.43%).

Overall, it is evident that geographical factors significantly influence the disparity in literacy rates across tehsils in Amravati district. As the district headquarters, Amravati benefits from better educational facilities, resulting in the highest literacy rate. Conversely, Dharni and Chikhaldara, being hilly, forested, remote, and tribal-dominated areas, show lower literacy rates.

Gender Disparity in Literacy in Amravati District (Year 2011):

Based on Table 1, it is observed that Amravati tehsil has the highest number of literate women (307,041) and men (338,423) compared to other tehsils in the district. The highest gender gap (9.21%) is found in Chikhaldara tehsil, where the number of literate men is 44,187, while literate women are 33,249. Following Chikhaldara, Dharni tehsil shows a gender gap of 8.71%. Factors such as tribal dominance, hilly terrain, and remote locations contribute to the highest gender gap in these areas.

In Amravati tehsil, the percentage of literate men is 42.92%, and that of literate women is 38.94%, resulting in a gender disparity of only 3.98%. Amravati tehsil exhibits the lowest gender gap across the district. Being the educational hub, Amravati city offers better educational facilities, reducing the disparity significantly.

The low gender gap category (less than 4%) includes only Amravati tehsil (3.98%). The medium gender gap category (4% to 8%) includes about 8 tehsils. The high gender gap category (greater than 8%) includes Chikhaldara (9.21%) and Dharni (8.71%) tehsils.

Table 2
Tehsil-wise Gender Disparity Index Calculated for Amravati District

Sr. No.	Gender Disparity Capacity	Gender Disparity Group	No. of Tehsils	Names of Tehsils
1	Low (0.060 or less)	Low	01	Amravati (0.053)
2	Moderate (0.060–0.090)	Moderate	11	Nandgaon (0.087), Bhankuli (0.087), Tiwsa (0.082), Dhamangaon Railway (0.082), Chandur Railway (0.081), Warud (0.081), Morshi (0.078), Achalpur (0.077), Daryapur (0.076), Anjangaon Surji (0.075), Chandur Bazaar (0.075)
3	High (Above 0.090)	High	02	Chikhaldara (0.147), Dharni (0.140)

Amravati District: Pattern of Gender Disparity in Literacy - 2011

Table No. 2 illustrates the distribution of literacy disparity indices across tehsils in the Amravati district. From this, it is evident that there is a tehsil-wise variation in literacy disparities within the district. The highest gender disparity index category includes Chikhaldara and Dharni tehsils. The medium gender disparity index category comprises about 11 tehsils, including Nandgaon Khandeshwar, Bhatkuli, Achalpur, Daryapur, Morshi, Warud, etc. The low gender disparity index category includes only the Amravati tehsil, where the gap between male and female literacy rates is minimal.

In Amravati, which has achieved development in economic, cultural, industrial, trade, business, educational, and other sectors, this gap is negligible. However, in the municipal areas of the other 11 tehsils, a moderate disparity is observed. Furthermore, in tehsils like Chikhaldara and Dharni, which are characterized by hilly terrain, forested areas, lack of transportation facilities, religious practices, superstitions, and tribal-dominated regions, the literacy rate of women is significantly lower compared to men. As a result, these tehsils exhibit higher gender disparities in literacy compared to others.

Conclusion:

From the above discussion, it is evident that various factors such as economic, social, political, religious, and traditional cultural influences significantly affect gender disparity in literacy across the tehsils of Amravati district. Among the 14 tehsils in the district, Chikhaldara and Dharni have the lowest literacy rates and the highest gender disparity indices. Overall, the literacy rate of women in these tehsils is notably lower compared to men.

Amravati city, being the central hub of the district and the main educational center of West Vidarbha, offers comprehensive educational facilities, from pre-primary to higher education. As a result, Amravati tehsil records the highest literacy rate (81.88%) and the lowest gender disparity index.

Efforts at government, semi-government, and private levels to establish gender equality, along with positive changes in societal attitudes towards female literacy, and initiatives like "Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao," have contributed to an increase in the literacy rate of women in the district. These initiatives have been instrumental in reducing gender disparity and promoting the literacy rate among women in Amravati district.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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